

DURABILITY OF ISOTHERMALLY AGED POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Several composite material systems representing different classes of polymer materials have been selected for an isothermal aging program designed to assess the durability of these systems when exposed to temperatures up to 232°C/450°F. Data discussed will include results up to 10,000 hours of aging. Properties that are monitored include weight loss, glass transition temperature, and various mechanical properties. The results of these studies have identified systems which have better temperature stability and have helped identify some of the dominant degradation processes that effect residual physical and mechanical properties. This data is being used to develop strength and life prediction analyses which in turn will be used for screening potential accelerated aging methodologies.

KEYWORDS: composite durability, long term aging, accelerated aging, residual strength, prediction methodology, oxidation/diffusion

INTRODUCTION

An understanding of advanced polymeric matrix composite (PMC) material durability behavior in the extreme flight regimes associated with the High Speed Civil Transport (HSCT) is necessary before these materials can be implemented. PMC materials under development for advanced military aircraft may meet these durability requirements, but are costly and not optimized for the long-term elevated temperature HSCT environment. Long-term and accelerated test procedures and methods are required to shorten the development and verification time of new PMC materials for the HSCT.

Under the High Speed Research program, NASA and an industry team, composed of The Boeing Company, McDonnell Douglas Aerospace, Lockheed-Martin Aeronautical Systems, and Northrop-Grumman Corporation, are working together to assess the long term durability of candidate polymer matrix composite material systems. This work is divided into three tasks: Database Generation, Prediction Methodology, and Accelerated Aging Test Methodology. Efforts conducted under this program in each of these areas has provided the foundation for the current NASA/Industry Materials and Structures Program for the HSCT.

The database generation task is designed to provide test data for material systems which have been exposed to real time, long term exposure conditions. This is being accomplished in a building block fashion which allows for an understanding of the individual factors which control the mechanisms which dominate the material performance. Aging conditions include isothermal aging, isothermal aging with an applied constant axial load, thermal cycling, and thermomechanical fatigue. It is also in this task in which real time, long term flight profile testing is being conducted. Large composite panels have been placed in test frames with ovens and are being subject to a simulated flight profile. These tests will be conducted for up

to 60,000 hours and will provide the necessary real time data to which the accelerated test methods will be compared for purposes of verification.

In the accelerated test methodology task, additional testing is being performed to examine how it may be possible to accelerate the aging process in the composite materials without changing the degradation mechanism as compared to the real time test results. Changing the damage mechanism would invalidate the accelerated test technique. To accomplish this goal, additional testing is performed to specifically examine those factors and their magnitudes which have the most effect on material behavior, both physically and mechanically. Examples of the types of aging conditions are: isothermal aging at temperatures slightly below the glass transition temperature, changing the exposure environment (i.e. argon, air, oxygen), examining the effects of moisture and ultraviolet radiation, etc.. Essentially, the concept is to make use of those environmental factors that the aircraft will be exposed to naturally and increase their magnitude to determine if the aging process can be accelerated. And if so, how fast can it be accelerated. This task also allows for the examination of synergistic effects associated with exposing the composite material system to two or more environmental conditions at the same time.

Once an understanding of how the material behaves under different exposure conditions is obtained, then analysis methods may be developed and used to predict the material performance. This is being accomplished under the prediction methodology task. These methods will be used to help define the exact accelerated test conditions needed to accelerate the aging process for a material system. It is important to note that the accelerated test methods will be material dependent. It is presumptuous to believe that all material age the same way and therefore will degrade identically. In this program, we have selected candidate and model materials for evaluation. The candidate material is one which is hoped will show little or no degradation over 1 lifetime of aging. While that means the material is good for the aircraft, it tells us little of how to accelerate the aging process in the material. Therefore, model materials are also chosen which are known to degrade over 1 lifetime of exposure. Ideally, the chosen model material is of the same family as the candidate material such that any accelerated methods that are proven to work for the model system may also work for the candidate system over a longer period of time.

DATABASE GENERATION

In the Database Generation task, efforts are focused on the selection and screening of candidate polymeric composite materials that showed potential to operate for long duration (>60,000 hours) at temperatures between 121°C/250°F and 177°C/350°F. Eight (8) material systems were initially selected for a series of mechanical and physical screening tests after isothermal aging as shown in Figure 1. The objective of these screening tests was to select three (3) material systems for extensive long-term thermal aging studies and to select two (2) material systems for accelerated test methodology development. Results discussed will include test data of material systems aged up to 10,000 hours [1]. Aging of these systems will continue past 60,000 hours.

A series of physical/chemical tests were performed on each of the eight screening materials to: 1) characterize the material systems for comparison with each other, 2) establish baseline values for each of the material systems for later comparison with aged data; and 3) develop possible screening tools. Each of these physical/chemical tests provided information about

the material system on the molecular or microscopic level as compared to the mechanical testing that provided data on a macroscopic scale. It is critical that data from both the microscopic and macroscopic scales be gathered on these materials systems for comparison and correlation. At the temperatures of the HSCT flight environment, the long-term durability of a material system depends ultimately on the molecular properties of the polymer chain and on the interface of the resin with the carbon fibers as well as their microscopic order or morphology. In addition, it is crucial to establish and understand the nature of the molecular-structure/macroscopic property relationships that exist in these high performance polymer systems if meaningful accelerated aging studies are to be conducted.

Weight change and microcracking measurements shown in Figures 2 and 3 were made periodically to determine the effect of aging at the various temperatures on the different material properties. It is obvious from these measurements that the thermoplastic IM7/ITX and the thermoplastic/polyimide IM7/K3B appear to have been the least affected by the aging conditions. Based on these results, these two materials and a third, G40-800/XU71787.09L cyanate ester, were chosen for more extensive mechanical testing and evaluation. Both IM7/ITX and IM7/K3B were considered candidate HSCT material systems at 149°C/300°F and 177°C/350°F, respectively. The cyanate ester system, G40-800/XU71787.09L, was chosen as a model material system at 177°C/350°F.

Mechanical tests conducted on IM7/ITX, IM7/K3B, and G40-800/XU71787.09L included open-hole tension, open hole compression, and compression strength after impact on quasi-isotropic laminates. Data from these tests are shown in Figures 4 and 5. Glass transition temperature measurements also shown in Figure 5 were also made on the unaged and aged material. The data is consistent in that the IM7/K3B and IM7/ITX material systems show no statistical degradation in mechanical properties, while the G40-800/XU71787.09L material system does. Glass transition temperature increased with aging time for IM7/ITX, was constant for IM7/K3B, and decreased for G40-800/XU71787.09L.

ACCELERATED TEST METHODOLOGY

The goal in this effort was to establish a method for obtaining end-of-life thermomechanical properties of advanced polymer matrix composites through accelerated aging. Considering that future aircraft require two lifetimes of testing to meet reliability requirements as currently outlined by the Federal Aviation Administration, a means of obtaining certification in an accelerated fashion is required. This accelerated certification testing must simulate flight and produce the failure modes and property degradation expected during the aircraft lifetime.

An environment screening program was performed to identify test parameters and magnitudes required to accelerate the aging process. The test program included exposure temperatures of 177°C/350°F, 193°C/380°F, 204°C/400°F, and 232°C/450°F, and pressure levels of 0.14 atm, 1.0 atm, and 6.8 atm. Exposure times ranged from 250 hours to 2000 hours. Panel lay-up was a 16 ply quasi-isotropic panel [45/0/-45/90]_{2s}. Studies for this effort concentrated on two polymeric composite material systems; IM7/K3B and G40-800/XU71787.09L. Chemical, physical and mechanical studies were conducted on specimens after exposure to the various accelerated aging environments. Weight loss was large for the G40-800/XU71787.09L material system relative to IM7/K3B. This data is plotted in Figure 6.

An empirical model was developed to predict weight loss response of the G40-800/XU71787.09L system to temperature and pressure. Data correlation with this model is provided Figure 7. This model assumed a diffusion controlled process through the thickness of the laminate. Diffusivity data was calculated for each weight loss curve and plotted to provide relationships with exposure temperature, pressure, and time. Edge effects were also accounted for by dividing the diffusivity by a geometry dependent factor.

The model was used to define accelerated aging environments based on the premise that equivalent laminate weight loss results in equivalent damage. Three accelerated aging conditions were defined to provide identical weight loss measurements to real time aging conditions for the G40-800/XU71787.09L material system:

Real Time Aging Condition	Accelerated Test Condition (ATC)
177°C/350°F, 1.0 atm, 5000 hours	204°C/400°F , 1.0 atm, 960 hours (ATC #1)
177°C/350°F, 1.0 atm, 5000 hours	182°C/360°F , 6.8 atm, 990 hours (ATC #2)
177°C/350°F, 1.0 atm, 10000 hours	204°C/400°F , 1.0 atm, 2000 hours (ATC #3)

A second set of G40-800/XU71787.09L panels with different length to width ratios as compared to the original screening tests were aged under the real time and the accelerated aged conditions described above. Weight loss measurements compared very well with the model predictions. Weight loss for the 5000 hour real time condition and the two accelerated aging conditions (ATC #1 and ATC #2) was 0.57%. It should be noted that the model was derived with data which had accumulated at most 5000 hour of exposure time. Therefore, the 10000 hour weight loss prediction was an extrapolation of the available data and as a result was the case with the worst agreement with the data. In fact, it took 2900 hours of exposure at 204°C/400°F and 1.0 atm in order to match the 10000 hour weight loss measurement under real time conditions.

Mechanical property testing was also performed to determine if weight loss could be a tracking parameter to which mechanical property changes in the material system could be linked. Open hole tension and compression tests were conducted at room and elevated temperatures and compared to data from all aging conditions as shown in Figure 8. The data was plotted against the simulated time for the accelerated aging conditions. For all conditions except one the data from all aged conditions fell within the scatter band. Statistically, the accelerated aged conditions provided the same residual properties as the real time conditions. The one case in which that was not true was for the elevated temperature open hole compression test performed after 10000 hours of aging. The residual strength of the accelerated aged panel fell well below the residual strength of the real time aged panel.

The poor correlation after 10,000 hours at 204°C/400°F can be traced to the glass transition temperature of the material. Dynamic mechanical analysis of specimens from aged panels shows that the glass transition temperature changes significantly as the material ages as can be observed in Figure 9. For less than 5,000 hours, the glass transition temperature (T_g) does not change significantly at the two lower aging temperature; and little change is observed in the mechanical properties. After 10,000 hours at 177°C/350°F, the T_g is reduced to 242°C/468°F which is still well above the elevated test temperature of 177°C/350°F. For the ATC #3 (2,900 hours at 204°C/400°F) condition, however, the T_g has dropped to 182°C/360°F which is below the aging temperature and only 10°C above the test temperature. It is not surprising that the compression strength was severely degraded.

PREDICTION METHODOLOGY

Under the Prediction Methodology task, efforts are directed toward developing both a physical degradation (aging) model and a structural mechanics model to account for long term aging effects on the residual mechanical properties of polymer matrix composites. The long term goal of this work is to combine these models into one analysis package that would allow an engineer to predict residual properties of candidate polymer matrix composite materials after exposure to a typical HSCT environment. This will be particularly useful in defining accelerated aging thermomechanical spectra.

The overall predictive methodology for polymer composites has three parts. First, develop a model capable of predicting the change in a physical parameter, such as weight change or glass transition temperature, due to the exposure environment. Second, establish an empirical, material dependent relationship between the physical parameter and specific mechanical properties (i.e. stiffness, strength, etc.). Third, the “aged” lamina properties are fed into a laminate strength code to predict the residual properties of the laminate. The entire analysis package is called ISAAC (Integrated Strength Analysis for Aged Composites). Work is currently on-going in each of these three areas. The overall prediction methodology is being validated by predicting the results of the many aged laminate tests.

The physical aging model concentrated on an oxygen diffusion/oxidation model to analytically simulate the diffusion of oxygen into the composite and the subsequent oxidation of the polymer material [2-5]. Diffusion and reaction rate data was measured from controlled experiments on G40-800/XU71787.09L and IM7/K3B material systems. This data was used in a finite element model to measure the concentration of oxygen through the thickness of the laminate. The results are plotted in Figure 10. Based on photomicrographs of the surface layers, a two-phase model was developed which allowed a surface “ash” layer to form with different diffusion and reaction rate constants than the center core laminate. The model was correlated with “ash” layer thickness measurements as shown in Figure 11 for G40-800/XU71787.09L laminates aged at 149°C/300°F and 177°C/350°F [6].

The strength analysis portion of the ISAAC code allows prediction of laminate modulus [7] and strength based on constituent and ply properties. The analysis can be used for predicting unnotched and center notched laminates subject to axial and/or bending running loads [8, 9]. The analysis is done on a ply-by-ply basis and provides output every time a ply is predicted to fail. Failure modes are determined and specified based on ply failures. Multiple failure criteria are provided including maximum stress, maximum strain, modified maximum shear strain (based on work done by Hart-Smith [10]), Tsai-Hill, and Tsai-Wu. The effects of thermal residual stresses may also be included in the analysis.

This portion of the ISAAC code was designed to accept constituent and ply properties after being degraded due to long term exposure to harsh environments. Currently, the analysis can be used to predict the strength and stiffness of aged composite coupons when provided degraded constituent and lamina data. ISAAC predictions and test data for the G40-800/XU71787.09L material system are shown in Figure 12. The ply-by-ply nature of the input allows different levels of deterioration for layers closer to the surface of the laminate. The ISAAC code, in its current form, is well suited for performing trade studies to evaluate the effects of degradation on laminate mechanical performance. These trade studies have correlated laminate mechanical properties with ply degradation as a function of ply location in the laminate. These studies have been useful in defining the number of surface plies which

must be degraded in order to match aged material response. Although not completed, the long term goal for the ISAAC strength analysis code is to tie it to physical aging model which would determine the amount of degradation as a function of ply location and environment.

CONCLUSIONS

Key to the development of a High Speed Civil Transport is ensuring that the materials selected are capable of withstanding the exposure conditions for an estimated lifetime of 60,000 hours. However, without adequate test data, reliable prediction capability, and verifiable accelerated test methodology this cannot be accomplished. Each of these tasks are very important and rely on each other.

In this paper, a brief review is provided which demonstrates the type of data being developed under each of the three main tasks: Database Generation, Accelerated Test Methodology, and Prediction Methodology. Data is provided for several systems with particular attention focused on the cyanate ester material system, G40-800/XU71787.09L. This material system is a good example of one which shows significant degradation within the operating envelope of the HSCT. As a result this material is not considered a candidate material system. Testing on this system continued however, because it was originally considered a model material system. Further testing discovered its key degradation mechanism to be a drop in glass transition temperature as aging exposure time increased. This drop was accelerated at higher aging temperatures. In order to develop reliable and accurate prediction methods for G40-800/XU71787.09L, it would be necessary to map the glass transition temperature as a function of each exposure condition and then to model the effect of a change in T_g with changes in mechanical properties. However, since the degradation mechanism of G40-800/XU71787.09L is not the same as the candidate materials further work on this system is not required. Instead new model materials are now being defined and similar exploratory testing is underway.

It is prudent to point out that the risk associated with the development of accurate and reliable accelerated test techniques is high. In fact, it may be too lofty a goal. A more likely outcome of this work could be a series of screening tests to which a material would be subject. Further testing of the material system would be dependent on passing each preceding test series. If a material passes each test series, than it would be a candidate for long term exposure testing and eventual use on the aircraft. The testing and analytical efforts discussed are required to define these screening tests. Ideally, this work will provide a template which will define the types of tests that should be conducted on new materials as they become available.

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Material ID	Material Name	Polymer Family	Aging Temperatures		
			121°C/250°F	149°C/300°F	177°C/350°F
A	IM7/ITX	Thermoplastic	X	X	
B	IM7/SP500-2	Epoxy	X	X	
C	IM7/5250-4	Bismaleimide	X	X	
D	G60-600/5250-4	Bismaleimide	X	X	
E	IM7/3135	Bismaleimide		X	X
F	IM7/K3B	Polyimide		X	X
G	G40-800/XU71787.09L	Cyanate Ester		X	X
H	IM7/AB-BCB-MI	Benzocyclobutene		X	X

Figure 1: Polymer composites in durability program

Figure 2: Thermal aging screening

Material	Aging Temp °C/°F	5000 Hours aging		10000 Hours Aging	
		Center	Surface	Center	Surface
IM7/ITX	149/300	None	None	Several	Minor
IM7/SP500-2	149/300	Several	Several	Extensive	Extensive
IM7/5250-4	149/300	None	None	None	Minor
G60-600/5250-4	149/300	Several	Several	Several	Several
IM7/3135	177/350	None	Several	None	Several
IM7/K3B	177/350	None	None	None	Minor
G40-800/XU71787.09L	177/350	None	Major	None	Major

Figure 3: Microcracking studies after aging

Figure 4: Open hole tension and compression data

Figure 5: Compression after impact and glass transition temperature data

Figure 6: Accelerated weight loss data

Figure 7: Model weight loss predictions for G40-800/XU71787.09L

Figure 8: Accelerated and real time open hole tension and compression data

Figure 9: DMA data for G40-800/XU71787.09L

Figure 10: Oxygen diffusion model correlation

Figure 11: Ash layer model correlation

Figure 12: ISAAC strength predictions